

Ordering nanostructure and properties of Al₂O₃ /ZrO₂ eutectic ceramic composites prepared by combustion synthesis under low pressure

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Abstract: Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics were prepared by combustion synthesis using Al and Zr(NO₃)₄ as raw materials. Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic structure showed that randomly-oriented rod-like ZrO₂ phases were embedded in Al₂O₃ matrix with a spacing of about 280 nm. The bending strength and fracture toughness of the product reached 1060MPa and 11.2MPa·m^{1/2}, respectively, which were attributed to nanostructure eutectic, bridge and pull-out effects of the rod-like ZrO₂.

Keywords: Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics; microstructure; mechanical properties; combustion synthesis

1. Introduction

Recently, Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics are attracting considerable interest because of their combination of high strength and toughness at elevated temperatures due to the special fiber or lamellar structure [1-3]. At present, several advanced techniques are employed to prepare Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic, including Bridgman, laser heated floating zone (LHFZ), edge-defined film-fed growth (EFG) and micro-pulling down (μ -PD) method [4]. However, large bulk Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic in centimeter scale with fine interphase spacing (<1 μ m) is difficult to fabricate by employing the above mentioned methods. Combustion synthesis, which is a novel preparation and processing technique for high-temperature ceramic and compound, has the advantages of high reaction temperature (3000-4000K) and large thermal gradient (10³ -10⁶ K/cm) to prepare the large bulk eutectic ceramic [5,6]. Zhao *et al* reported the Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic with 30 cm diameter was fabricated by simultaneous thermit-combustion and gravity separation using CrO₃, Al, ZrO₂, Y₂O₃ and SiO₂ as raw materials [7], and Mei *et al* conducted a similar way to prepare Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic and studied the effect of gravity field on the microstructure of the products

[8].

In our previous work, the microstructure of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic coating prepared by combustion-assisted thermal explosion spraying was studied. The Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ coating can be divided into three regions according to the crystal structure along the growth direction. First region in contact with the Cu substrate was amorphous structure, and then was cellular crystal region, in which Al₂O₃ shows cystiform shape, and last dendrite Al₂O₃ crystal, the later-two of which was embedded in Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic matrix [9]. Moreover the Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramic composites were obtained by explosion synthesis [10], but it had the disadvantages that the pressure was higher than 30MPa and the size of products was smaller than $\Phi 20 \times 40$ mm. In this paper, Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics were fabricated by combustion synthesis under low pressure using Al and Zr(NO₃)₄ as raw materials. It had the advantages that the pressure was lower than 10MPa so that the safety of production could be ensured and large bulk products, which could reach $\Phi 60 \times 50$ mm, could be obtained.

2. Experimental procedure

Al powders (99% purity, 5 μ m) and Zr(NO₃)₄ (99% purity) were used as reactant. The reaction

was expected to take place as follow:

Through adding appropriate amount of Al_2O_3 and ZrO_2 into reactant, the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic ceramic could be obtained. In addition, the reaction temperature and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ ratio in products could be adjusted to study the reaction mechanism and eutectic microstructure. The reactant components with adiabatic temperature of 2800,3000,3200 and 3400K, which were marked as AT1,AT2,AT3 and AT4, respectively, were selected to study the effect of reactant content on reaction temperature.

The microstructure of eutectic ceramic was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6390, Japan). The phase compositions were determined by X-ray Diffraction (XRD, D/MAX-RB, Rigaku, Japan). The flexural strength was measured by a three-point bending method with a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min and a span of 30 mm and sample dimension of 3 mm × 4 mm × 36 mm on a universal testing machine (Instron-1186, USA).The fracture toughness was measured by single edge-notched beam method with a cross-head speed 0.05 mm/min. A notch with a depth of 2 mm and a width of 0.4 mm was machined into test bars of 2 mm × 4 mm × 22 mm.

3. Results and discussion

It could be found from Fig.1 that the products consisted of Al_2O_3 , ZrO_2 and ZrN . The existence of ZrN instead of AlN in products indicated that the reaction designed as equation (1) was unrealistic because of the unstability of AlN at high temperature. The product constitution as shown in Fig.1 indicated that the real reaction route should correspond to equation (2).

The relationship between adiabatic temperature and Gibbs Free Energy in reaction (2) was calculated, as shown in Fig.2. It indicated that the Gibbs Free Energy of this reaction would fall below zero when the temperature rose above 1399 K. Since all combustion temperatures were above

2800K, in this study, the AlN was transformed into ZrN at last.

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction pattern of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic ceramics (a) AT1 (b) AT2 (c) AT3 (d) AT4

Fig. 2 The relationship between T_{ad} and Gibbs Free Energy in reaction (2)

According to the reaction (2), in the closed reactor, a little content of nitrogen was released to produce pressure. The pressure was calculated according to ideal gas equation of state and measured (samples AT1, AT2, AT3, AT4) by piezometer, as shown in Fig.3. The measured pressure was little higher than the theoretical calculated pressure and the highest measured pressure was about 9MPa. Moreover, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{ZrO}_2$ eutectic ceramic could be prepared under greatly lower pressure or even atmospheric conditions if

excess Al was added into the reactant on the basis of the reaction equation (3) in further investigation.

Fig.3 The relationship between pressure and T_{ad} of the combustion synthesis for Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic

The adiabatic temperature was calculated through thermodynamic analysis, as shown in Fig.4. The measured reaction temperatures were marked in Fig.4. It was found that the measured temperature was about 200K lower than the theoretical temperature. The adiabatic temperature of this combustion reaction could easily reach 4000K, which was much higher than the eutectic transformation temperature of Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 system (2135 K) based on the Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 equilibrium phase diagram [11], indicating the method employed in this paper had the distinct advantage to prepare Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic. The reaction temperature curve measured by W/Re thermocouples was shown in Fig.5. The temperature curve had a sharp rise once the reactant mixture was ignited, which was corresponding to adiabatic hypothesis. In addition, the cooling rate of reaction product was obviously fast, as shown in Fig.5, which was favorable to obtain fine microstructure of Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic.

Fig.4 The relationship between T_{ad} and reactant content of the combustion synthesis for Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic

Fig.5 Temperature profile of the combustion synthesis for Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic ($T_{ad}=2673K$)

The backscattered electron image of the Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic ceramic was shown in Fig.6. It can be observed that rod-like ZrO_2 showed white and Al_2O_3 phase presented deep color in the magnification microstructure of Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic. The diameter and interphase spacing of the rod-like ZrO_2 was in submicrometer range of 200 nm and 280 nm, respectively. Such fine eutectic structure is likely caused by the large cooling rate of the product prepared by combustion synthesis.

In the simplest case of isotropic surface energy, ZrO_2 rods in Al_2O_3/ZrO_2 eutectic are anticipated to form when the volume fraction is less than 28%, while lamellas form when volume fraction is greater than 28%. In this study, the volume fraction

of ZrO₂ was less than 28%, and thus ZrO₂ exhibited the tendency to grow in the rod structure than lamellas.

Figure 7 showed the fracture morphology of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic composite. The fractography showed that pull-out of the ZrO₂ rod and crack deflection were the main fracture modes in Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic. Because the eutectic structure is in-situ formed in molten state during combustion synthesis process, nano-micron ZrO₂ rods are entirely embedded in the Al₂O₃ matrix, thus the prepared eutectic composite exhibits excellent mechanical properties. The maximum bending strength and fracture toughness of composites were 1060MPa and 11.2MPa·m^{1/2}, respectively.

Fig.6 Backscattered electron image of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic

Fig.7 Fractography of Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic

4. Conclusions

Al₂O₃/ZrO₂ eutectic ceramics were fabricated by combustion synthesis under low pressure using Al and Zr(NO₃)₄ as raw materials. The eutectic microstructure showed that rod-like ZrO₂ embedded in Al₂O₃ matrix with a spacing of 280 nm. Due to nanostructured eutectic, pull-out and bridge effects of rod-like ZrO₂, the bending strength and fracture toughness of the eutectic ceramic composites reached 1060MPa and 11.2MPa·m^{1/2}, respectively.

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